

TIME-TEMPERATURE-WATER ABSORPTION SUPERPOSITION PRINCIPLE FOR FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT: This paper is concerned with the influence of water absorption and dehydration on the time-temperature dependent flexural strength in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP laminate. The unidirectional CFRP laminates were treated under three conditions, “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry”. “Dry” specimens are dried in the oven after molding CFRP laminate. “Wet” specimens are made by soaking “Dry” specimen in hot water. “Wet + Dry” specimens are made by dehydrating “Wet” specimen in the oven. The three-point bending tests for these three kinds of specimens were carried out under various constant strain rates (CSR) and temperatures. As results, it was cleared that the flexural CSR strength in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP laminates depends on water absorption as well as time and temperature, and that the time-temperature-water absorption superposition principle holds for CSR strength of this CFRP laminate.

KEYWORDS: CFRP, Viscoelastic, Water absorption, Flexural strength, Time-temperature superposition principle

INTRODUCTION

Recently carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) has been used for the primary structures of airplane, spacecraft and others, in which the high reliability should be kept during the long term operation. Therefore, it is strongly expected that the accelerated testing methodology is established for the long-term life prediction of composite structures exposed under the actual environments such as temperature, water and others.

The mechanical behavior of polymer resins exhibits time and temperature dependence, which is called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Furthermore, the viscoelastic behavior of polymer resins also depends on water absorption. Thus, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of polymer composites significantly depends on water absorption as well as time and temperature.

This paper is concerned with the influence of water absorption on the time-temperature dependent flexural strength of CFRP laminates. The CFRP laminates were treated under three conditions of “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” after molding. Three-point bending tests for these three kinds of CFRP laminates were carried out under various constant strain rates (CSR) and creep loadings at various temperatures. The influence of water absorption on time-temperature dependent creep compliance and flexural CSR strength was discussed, and the applicability of time-temperatures-water absorption superposition principle was confirmed for the flexural CSR strength as well as the creep compliance.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of CFRP laminates

The CFRP laminates were formed by hot pressing fifteen prepreg sheets which consist of unidirectional carbon fiber (Fortafil 510) and epoxy resin (Cape 2002). Cure condition for CFRP laminate was 1 hour at 130°C. The fiber volume fraction of the laminates was approximately 53%. The thickness of CFRP laminate was 3mm. Three-point bending test specimens were cut to the transverse direction of fibers from this CFRP laminate. The length and width of specimens were 60mm and 25mm for creep test, 80mm and 10mm for CSR test.

The test specimens were treated under three conditions of “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry”. Details of treated conditions are shown in Table 1. The “Dry” specimens were obtained by holding the cured specimen in the oven at 150°C for 2 hours. The “Wet” specimens were obtained by soaking the “Dry” specimens in hot water at various temperatures and times. The “Wet + Dry”

Table 1 Treated conditions for Dry, Wet and Wet + Dry

		In oven	□	In water	□	In oven
Dry		150□×2h				
Wet	0.5%	150□×2h	□	95□×12h 80□×48h 50□×360h		□
	1.0%	150□×2h	□	95□×24h 80□×144h 50□×1200h		□
	2.0%	150□×2h	□	95□×48h 80□×528h		□
Wet + Dry		150□×2h	□	95□×48h	□	150□×2h

specimens were obtained by dehydrating the “Wet (2.0%)” specimens in the oven at 150°C for 2 hours.

Test procedure

The three point bending tests under creep and various constant strain rates loadings for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens were carried out under various temperatures. The conditions for these tests are shown in table 2. Three-point bending creep tests were carried out using a creep testing machine with a constant temperature chamber, the creep compliance D_c was calculated from the deflection δ at the center of specimen using the following equation:

$$D_c = \frac{4bh^3\delta}{PL^3} \quad (1)$$

where b , h are the width and thickness of specimen, respectively. P is the applied load. L is the span ($L=50\text{mm}$).

Three-point bending CSR tests were carried out using an Instron type universal testing machine with a constant temperature chamber, the flexural CSR strength σ_s was calculated from the maximum load P_{\max} using following equation:

$$\sigma_s = \frac{3P_{\max}L}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

where $L=60\text{mm}$ for CSR test.

In order to prevent the dryness of “Wet” specimen during creep and CSR tests, the specimens were wrapped in a vinyl bag with distilled water as shown in Fig.1

Table 2 Creep and CSR test conditions

(a) Creep test

Condition	Loading time t [min]	Test temperature T [°C]
Dry	1/60 - 1200	25, 50, 70, 80, 90
Wet (0.5, 1.0, 2.0%)	1/60 - 1200	25, 40, 45, 50, 60
Wet (2.0%) + Dry	1/60 - 1200	25, 50, 70, 80, 90

Note (): Water content W_w

(b) CSR test

Condition	Loading rate V [mm/min]	Test temperature T [°C]
Dry	0.02, 2, 200	25, 50, 80, 100, 120
Wet (1.0, 2.0%)	0.02, 2, 200	25, 50, 70, 80, 90
Wet (2.0%) + Dry	0.02, 2, 200	25, 50, 80, 100, 120

Note (): Water content W_w

Fig.1 Three-point bending test for “Wet” specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Creep compliance

The left side of Fig.2 shows the creep compliance D_c versus loading time t_c for “Dry”, “Wet ($W_w=0.5, 1.0, 2.0\%$)”, and “Wet + Dry” specimen, respectively. The master curves for D_c were constructed by shifting D_c at various constant temperatures T except reference temperature T_0 along the log scale of time t so that they overlap each other to form a single smooth curve as shown in the right side of each graph. Since the smooth master curve for each D_c can be obtained, the time-temperature superposition principle is applicable for each D_c .

The solid line and chain line in Fig.2 (b)-(d) show the master curve of D_c for specimens soaked at temperature $T_w=80$ and 50 °C, respectively. Since the master curves of D_c for same water content W_w agree well with each other, the master curve of D_c for wet specimens depend on the amount of water absorption regardless of soaking time and temperature. The master curve of D_c for “Wet + Dry” specimen is almost same to that for “Dry” specimen as shown in Fig.2 (e).

Time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0;x}(T)$ for a response x ($x=c$ for creep time, $x=s$ for time to CSR failure) at a reference temperature T_0 is defined by

$$\log a_{T_0;x}(T) = \log t_x - \log t_x' \quad (3)$$

where the t_x, t_x' are the relevant physical time and the associated reduced time. The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0;c}(T)$ for each D_c obtained experimentally in Fig.2 is plotted respectively Fig.3. The $a_{T_0;c}(T)$ for each D_c are described by two Arrhenius' equations with different activation energies ΔH ,

$$\log a_{T_0;x}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \quad (4)$$

where G is gas constant 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K·mol)].

From Fig.3, it was cleared that the knee point temperature of $a_{T_0;c}(T)$ decreases remarkably with increasing water contents W_w , and that returned to the original one by drying after water absorption.

Fig.2 Master curves of creep compliance for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens

Fig.3 Time-temperature shift factor of creep compliance for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens

Flexural CSR strength

The left side of Fig.4 (a)-(d) shows the flexural CSR strength σ_s versus time to failure t_s at various temperatures T for “Dry”, “Wet (1.0, 2.0%)” and “Wet + Dry” specimens, where t_s is the time period from initial loading to maximum load during testing. The master curves of σ_s were constructed by shifting σ_s at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t_s based on same method to that for D_c . Since the smooth master curve of σ_s for each specimen can be obtained as shown in the right side of each graph, the time-temperature superposition principle is also applicable for each σ_s . From these figure, it was cleared that σ_s decreases with water absorption, and did not return perfectly to that of “Dry” specimen by drying after water absorption.

The time- temperature shift factors $a_{T_0:s}(T)$ for these σ_s are shown in Fig.5 together with those for D_c . The $a_{T_0:s}(T)$ of σ_s for each specimen agree well with that of D_c for corresponding specimen. Furthermore, $a_{T_0:s}(T)$ for σ_s returns to that for “Dry” specimen by drying after water absorption.

Time-temperature-water absorption superposition principle

The left side of Fig.6 shows the master curves of D_c for “Dry”, “Wet (1.0, 1.5, 2.0%)” and “Wet + Dry” specimens. The grand-master curve for D_c were constructed by shifting these master curves D_c at various water contents along the log scale of reduced time t' so that they overlap on D_c at the reference water content $W_{w0}=0\%$ (Dry) to form a single smooth grand-master curve as shown in the right side of this figure. Since all any master curves of D_c can be overlapped each other, the time-temperature-water absorption superposition principle is applicable for D_c .

The time-water content shift factor $a_{W_{w0}:x}(W_w)$ for a response x ($x=c$ for creep time, $x=s$ for time to CSR failure) at a reference amount of water absorption W_{w0} is defined by

$$\log a_{W_{w0}:x}(W_w) = \log t_x' - \log t_x'' \quad (5)$$

where t_x' , t_x'' are the associated reduce time and reduced-reduced time. The $a_{W_{w0}:x}(W_w)$ obtained experimentally from Fig.6 were plotted in Fig.7.

The left side of Fig.8 shows the master curves of σ_s for “Dry”, “Wet (1.0, 2.0%)” and “Wet + Dry” specimens. A smooth gland-master curve of σ_s was obtained by shifting master curves of σ_s for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens along the log scale of reduced time to failure t_s' as shown in the right side of Fig.8. Therefore, the time-temperature-water absorption superposition

Fig.4 Master curves of flexural CSR strength for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens

Figure 5 Time-temperature shift factor of flexural CSR strength for “Dry”, “Wet” and “Wet + Dry” specimens principle also holds for σ_s . The $a_{W_{wo:s}}(W_w)$ obtained experimentally from Fig.8 were plotted in Fig.9. The $a_{W_{wo:s}}(W_w)$ of σ_s agrees well with that of D_c for $W_w=1.0\%$. However, the $a_{W_{wo:s}}(W_w)$ of σ_s is larger than that of D_c for $W_w=2.0\%$, and does not return to that for “Dry” specimen by drying after water absorption of $W_w=2.0\%$. It can be considered that this phenomenon is due to the damage generated during water absorption.

Fig.6 Grand master curve of creep compliance

Fig.7 Time-temperature-water absorption shift factor of creep compliance

Fig.8 Grand master curve of flexural CSR strength

Fig.9 Time-temperature-water absorption shift factor of flexural CSR strength

Figure 10 show the SEM photograph of “Dry”, “Wet (1.0, 2.0%)” and “Wet + Dry” specimens after flexural CSR test at loading rate $V=2\text{mm/min}$ and test temperature $T=25^\circ\text{C}$. The “Dry” and “Wet ($W_w=1.0\%$, $T_w=95^\circ\text{C}$)” specimens were failed mainly by cohesive fracture of matrix resin. The “Wet ($W_w=2.0\%$, $T_w=95^\circ\text{C}$)” and “Wet + Dry” specimens were failed mainly by interfacial fracture of carbon fiber between matrix resin. It can be presumed that this change of fracture is caused by water absorption, and corresponds to the phenomenon for $a_{W_{w_0:s}}(W_w)$.

(a) Dry

(c) Wet ($W_w=2.0\%$, $T_w=95^\circ\text{C}$)

(b) Wet ($W_w=1.0\%$, $T_w=95^\circ\text{C}$)

(d) Wet + Dry

Fig.10 SEM photograph of flexural CSR strength

CONCLUSION

The influences of water absorption on the time-temperature dependent flexural strength of CFRP laminate were studied experimentally. We obtained following results:

- (1) The creep compliance and flexural CSR strength of CFRP laminates change with increasing of water content as well as time and temperature.
- (2) The time-temperature superposition principle holds for the creep compliance and flexural CSR strength for all specimens “Dry” “Wet”, and “Wet + Dry” regard less of water absorption.
- (3) The time-temperature-water absorption superposition principle holds for CSR strength as well as creep compliance of this CFRP laminate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the National Science Foundation (NSF) for funding this research (No. CMS-9812758).

REFERENCE

1. Aboudi, J. and Cederbaum, G. 1989. Analysis of Viscoelastic Laminated Composite Plates, *Composite Structures*, 12: 243-256
2. Sullivan, J. L. 1990. Creep and Physical Aging of Composites, *Composite Science and Technology*, 39: 207-232
3. Gates, T. 1992. Experimental characterization of nonlinear rate dependent behavior in advanced polymer matrix composites, *Experimental Mechanics*, 68-73
4. Miyano, Y., Kanemitsu, M., Kunio, T. and Kuhn, H. 1986. Role of Matrix Resin on Fracture Strengths of unidirectional CFRP, *J. Composite Materials*, 20: 520-538

5. Miyano, Y., McMurray, M. K., Enyama, J., and Nakada, M. 1994. Loading Rate and Temperature Dependence on Flexural Fatigue Behavior of a Satin Woven CFRP Laminate, *J. Composite Materials*, 28: 1250-1260
6. Miyano, Y., K. McMurray, M., Kitade, N., Nakada, M. and Mohri, M. 1994. Role of Matrix Resin on the Flexural Static Behavior of Unidirectional Pitch Based Carbon Fiber Laminates, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 4: 87-99
7. Miyano, Y., Nakada, M., and McMurray, M. K. 1995. Influence of Stress Ratio on Fatigue Behavior in Transverse Direction of Unidirectional CFRPs, *J. Composite Materials*, 29: 1808-1822
8. Miyano, Y., Nakada, M., McMurray, M. K. and Muki, R. 1997. Prediction of Flexural Fatigue Strength of CFRP Composites under Arbitrary Frequency, Stress Ratio and Temperature, *J. Composite Materials*, 31: 619-638
9. Shen, C. H and Springer, G. S. 1976. Moisture Absorption and Desorption of Composite Materials, *J. Composite Materials*, 10: 2-20
10. Neumann, S. and Marom, G. 1985. Stress Dependence of the Coefficient of Moisture Diffusion in Composite Materials, *Polymer Composites*, 6: 9-12
11. Selzer, R., and Friedrich, K. 1997. Mechanical properties and failure behaviour of carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composites under the influence of moisture, *Composites Part A*, 28A: 595-604